

Certain New Generalized Fractional Hermite-Hadamard Type Inequalities For Twice Differentiable Functions

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Abstract

Integral inequalities involving fractional operators have also been an active area of research. These inequalities play a crucial role in establishing bounds, estimates, and stability conditions for solutions to fractional integrals. I will investigate a unified approach, specifically for the midpoint and trapezoid rules, and discuss how to obtain these inequalities for s -convex functions. Moreover, I will explore their versions in fractional integrals, showcasing their flexibility in handling diverse fractional calculus operations. Furthermore, by using different values of the parameter, we obtain Simpson's type inequalities.

1. Introduction

The theory of convexity serves as a versatile framework for tackling problems across numerous fields. Convexity plays a crucial role in the study and development of integral inequalities. It offers key insights and tools for deriving bounds and estimating the behavior of integrals, particularly in relation to convex functions. These applications make convexity a fundamental concept in advancing the understanding of various inequality structures. The well-known definition and generalized convexity is stated as follows:

Definition 1 [1] *The mapping of $f : I \subseteq \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be convex if:*

$$f(ta + (1-t)b) \leq tf(a) + (1-t)f(b),$$

for all $a, b \in I$ and $t \in [0, 1]$

Definition 2 [2] *The function $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be s -convex (in the second sense) for $s \in (0, 1]$ if the following inequality holds*

$$f(ta + (1-t)b) \leq t^s f(a) + (1-t)^s f(b),$$

for all $a, b \in I$ and $t \in [0, 1]$

Integral inequalities are important mathematical tools used to establish bounds and relationships between integrals of functions. They help in estimating the behavior of functions over specific intervals and provide essential techniques for analyzing various mathematical problems. These inequalities have widespread applications in areas such as analysis, probability, and numerical integration, offering valuable insights into function properties and solution behaviors. The Hermite-Hadamard type (H-H) inequality is one of these. The Hermite-Hadamard type (H-H) inequality [3] has important applications in various fields, including analysis, optimization, and economics. Additionally, the inequality has extensions and generalizations to different settings, such as functions defined on convex sets. The Hermite-Hadamard type (H-H) inequality, named after Charles Hermite and Jacques Hadamard, has indeed been extensively studied and generalized over the years, making it an essential tool in mathematical analysis. Researchers have made significant contributions to its development and extension to various contexts, enriching its applicability and utility in different areas of mathematics and beyond. The classical Hermite-Hadamard inequality is stated as follows:

$$f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \leq \frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2}.$$

The exploration of this inequality in various generalizations, extensions, and refinements of the Hermite-Hadamard type (H-H) inequality, involving different types of functions, operators, and integral formulations. Here are some notable examples of such efforts. Alqahtani et al [4] derived Hermite-Hadamard type (H-H) inequalities for Caputo-Fabrizio operator. Yang et al [5] established Hermite-Hadamard type (H-H) inequalities using the strongly (s, m) -convex functions.

The classical Midpoint-type and Trapezoid-type inequalities for twice continuously differentiable functions are expressed as follows:

Theorem 1 *Let us note that $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a twice differentiable function on (a, b) , and let us consider*

$$\|f''\|_{\infty} = \sup_{x \in (a, b)} |f''(x)| < \infty. \text{ Then, the following inequalities}$$

hold:

$$\left| f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{24} \|f''\|_{\infty} (b-a)^2, \quad (1)$$

and

$$\left| \frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2} - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{12} \|f''\|_{\infty} (b-a)^2. \quad (2)$$

In the literature, different upper bounds for the errors (1) and (2) have been obtained by employing various function classes to estimate the error. In [6, 7] S. S. Dragomir proved the midpoint, and trapezoid quadrature formula for bounded variation.

Theorem 2 *Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a mapping of bounded variation on $[a, b]$. Then we have the inequalities:*

$$\left| f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{2} \bigvee_a^b(f),$$

and

$$\left| \frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2} - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{2} \bigvee_a^b(f),$$

where $\bigvee_a^b(f)$ denotes the total variation of f on the interval $[a, b]$.

In [8] U. S. Kirmaci established the midpoint inequality for differentiable function in [9], and S. S. Dragomir developed inequalities for differentiable mappings and give applications to special means of real numbers, and trapezoidal formula.

Theorem 3 Suppose $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a differentiable mapping on (a, b) such that $f' \in L[a, b]$. If $|f'|$ is convex on $[a, b]$, then we have

$$\left| f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{8} (b-a) \left[|f'(a)| + |f'(b)| \right] \quad (3)$$

and

$$\left| \frac{f(a)+f(b)}{2} - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{8} (b-a) \left[|f'(a)| + |f'(b)| \right] \quad (4)$$

In [10, 11] M. Z. Sarikaya generalized the midpoint, and trapezoidal type inequalities for twice differentiable function.

Theorem 4 Suppose $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a twice differentiable mapping on (a, b) such that $f'' \in L[a, b]$. If $|f''|$ is convex on $[a, b]$, then we have

$$\left| f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{48} \left[|f''(a)| + |f''(b)| \right]$$

and

$$\left| \frac{f(a)+f(b)}{2} - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{24} \left[|f''(a)| + |f''(b)| \right]$$

In [12] S. S. Dragomir presented the double inequality as follows:

Theorem 5 Suppose that $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is an s -convex function in the second sense, where $s \in (0, 1]$. Then we have the following Hermite-Hadamard inequality:

$$2^{s-1} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \leq \frac{f(a)+f(b)}{s+1}.$$

In [13, 14] M. W. Alomari, and U. S. Kirmaci derived the Hermite-Hadamard type inequality for s -convex as follows:

Theorem 6 Suppose $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a differentiable mapping on (a, b) such that $f' \in L[a, b]$. If $|f'|$ is s -convex on $[a, b]$, for some fixed $s \in (0, 1]$, then we have

$$\left| f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{b-a}{4} \frac{2^{s-2} + 1}{(s+1)(s+2)} \left[|f'(a)| + |f'(b)| \right]$$

and

$$\left| \frac{f(a)+f(b)}{2} - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{b-a}{2^{s+2}} \frac{s2^s + 1}{(s+1)(s+2)} \left[|f'(a)| + |f'(b)| \right]$$

In [15, 16] M. Z. Sarikaya introduced the midpoint, and trapezoidal type inequalities for the s -convex function in the second sense.

Theorem 7 Suppose $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a twice differentiable mapping on (a, b) such that $f'' \in L[a, b]$. If $|f''|$ is s -convex on $[a, b]$, then we have

$$\left| f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{2^{s+4}} \frac{2^{s+4} - (4s+12)}{(s+1)(s+2)(s+3)} \left[|f''(a)| + |f''(b)| \right]$$

and

$$\left| \frac{f(a)+f(b)}{2} - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{2(s+2)(s+3)} \left[|f''(a)| + |f''(b)| \right]$$

By introducing new operator, establishing novel inequalities, deriving interesting identities, exploring special cases, and demonstrating practical applications, the paper contributes to the ongoing development and enrichment of mathematical theory and its applications. We recall some well known operator as follows.

Definition 3 [17] Let $f \in H^1(a, b)$, $a < b$ for all $\alpha \in [0, 1]$, where $\beta(\alpha) > 0$ is a normalizer satisfying $\beta(0) = \beta(1) = 1$, then the left and right Caputo-Fabrizio fractional integrals are defined by:

$$\left({}_a^{CF} I^\alpha f \right)(x) = \frac{1-\alpha}{\beta(\alpha)} f(x) + \frac{\alpha}{\beta(\alpha)} \int_a^x f(x) dx$$

$$\left({}_b^{CF} I^\alpha f \right)(x) = \frac{1-\alpha}{\beta(\alpha)} f(x) + \frac{\alpha}{\beta(\alpha)} \int_x^b f(x) dx.$$

In [18] A. Fahad obtained the some novel inequalities for Caputo Fabrizio fractional integrals involving (α, s) -convex function as follows:

Theorem 8 A function $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a differentiable function on $[a, b]$. If $|f'|$ is (α, s) -convex function on $[a, b]$, then the following fractional inequality holds:

$$\left| \frac{(x-a)f(a)+(b-x)f(b)}{(b-a)} - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(b-a)} \left[({}^{CF}I_a^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_b^\alpha f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k) \right| \leq \frac{(x-a)^2}{(b-a)} \left[\frac{|f'(x)|}{(\alpha s+1)(\alpha s+2)} + \frac{|f'(a)|}{\alpha s+2} \right] + \frac{(b-x)^2}{b-x} \left[\frac{|f'(x)|}{(\alpha s+1)(\alpha s+2)} + \frac{|f'(b)|}{\alpha s+2} \right].$$

In [19] W. Afzal proved the midpoint type inequalities for h -Godunova Levin as follows:

Theorem 9 A function $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be an $[h_1, h_2]$ -convex function on $[a, b]$ and $f \in L_1[a, b]$ is (α, s) -convex function on $[a, b]$, $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, then the following fractional inequality holds:

$$\frac{1}{2 \left[H\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}\right) \right]} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \leq \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(b-a)} \left[({}^{CF}I_a^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_b^\alpha f)(k) \right] \leq \left(|f'(a)| + |f'(b)| \right) \int_0^1 H(x, 1-x) dx - \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k).$$

Inequalities for three times differentiable mappings and applications to special means are given by Qaisar et. al [20].

Theorem 10 Let $f : I \subset \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a differentiable function on I° , $a, b \in I^\circ$ with $a < b$. If $f''' \in L[a, b]$ is convex on $[a, b]$, then the following inequality holds:

$$\left| \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(b-a)} \left[({}^{CF}I_a^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_b^\alpha f)(k) \right] - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - \frac{(b-a)^2}{24} f''\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right| \leq \frac{(b-a)^3}{384} \left(|f'''(a)| + |f'''(b)| \right).$$

The purpose of this paper is to present a unified approach, specifically to Midpoint and trapezoid type inequalities of the twice differentiable functions for Caputo-Fabrizio fractional integrals.

2 An Critical Identity

To establish the results of this section regarding Caputo-Fabrizio fractional integral operators, we start by proving the following lemma:

Lemma 1 Let $I \subset \mathbb{R}$ be an open interval, $a, b \in I$ with a, b . If $f : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a twice differentiable function such that f'' is integrable then for $0 \leq r \leq 1$, the following equality holds:

$$\frac{B(\alpha)}{\alpha(b-a)} \left[({}^{CF}I_a^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_b^\alpha f)(k) \right] - (1-r)f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - r \left[\frac{f(a)+f(b)}{2} \right] - \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\alpha(b-a)} f(k) = (b-a)^2 \int_0^1 M(t, r) f''(ta + (1-t)b) dt,$$

where

$$M(t, r) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}t(t-r) & t \in \left[0, \frac{1}{2}\right], \\ \frac{1}{2}(1-t)(1-r-t) & t \in \left(\frac{1}{2}, 1\right]. \end{cases}$$

By Simple computational we obtain the required result. For the simplicity of the notation, for a twice differentiable mapping f with $|f''| \in M_s^2[a, b]$, let

$$N_a^b(f)(r, s) = \frac{B(\alpha)}{\alpha(b-a)} \left[({}^{CF}I_a^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_b^\alpha f)(k) \right] - (1-r)f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - r \left[\frac{f(a)+f(b)}{2} \right] - \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\alpha(b-a)} f(k).$$

Theorem 11 Under the assumptions of Lemma 1 holds. If $|f''|$ is s -convex function on $[a, b]$, then following inequality for holds:

$$(a) \text{ for } 0 \leq r \leq \frac{1}{2} : \frac{2}{(b-a)^2} |N_a^b(f)(r, s)| \leq (\Pi_{11}(r, s) + \Pi_{12}(r, s) + \Pi_{13}(r, s) + \Pi_{14}(r, s)) \left(|f''(a)| + |f''(b)| \right),$$

where

$$\Pi_{11}(r, s) = \frac{r^{s+3}}{(s+2)(s+3)}.$$

$$\Pi_{12}(r, s) = \frac{r^{s+3}}{(s+2)(s+3)} - \frac{2r(s+3) - (s+2)}{2^{s+3}(s+2)(s+3)}.$$

$$\Pi_{13}(r, s) = \frac{(1-r)^{s+2}(rs+r+2)}{(s+1)(s+2)(s+3)} + \frac{2r(s+3)^2 - (s^2+7s+14)}{2^{s+3}(s+1)(s+2)(s+3)}$$

$$\Pi_{14}(r, s) = \frac{(1-r)^{s+2}(rs+r+2)}{(s+1)(s+2)(s+3)} - \frac{rs+3r-2}{(s+1)(s+2)(s+3)}$$

for $\frac{1}{2} \leq r \leq 1$:

Proof. Using the lemma 1, we

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{2}{(b-a)^2} |N_a^b(f)(r, s)| &\leq \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} |t(t-r)| |f''(ta+(1-t)b)| dt \\ &+ \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^1 |(1-t)(1-r-t)| |f''(ta+(1-t)b)| dt \\ &= P_{11} + P_{22}. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

(a) for $0 \leq r \leq \frac{1}{2}$ and fact that $|f''|$ is s -convex function, we have

$$\begin{aligned} P_{11} &\leq \left\{ \int_0^r t^{s+1}(r-t) dt + \int_r^{\frac{1}{2}} t^{s+1}(t-r) dt \right\} |f''(a)| \\ &+ \left\{ \int_0^r t(r-t)(1-t)^s dt + \int_r^{\frac{1}{2}} t(t-r)(1-t)^s dt \right\} |f''(b)| \\ &= [\Pi_{11}(r, s) + \Pi_{12}(r, s)] |f''(a)| + [\Pi_{13}(r, s) + \Pi_{14}(r, s)] |f''(b)|, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} P_{22} &\leq \left\{ \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{1-r} (1-t)(1-r-t)t^s dt + \int_{1-r}^1 (1-t)(t+r-1)t^s dt \right\} |f''(a)| \\ &+ \left\{ \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{1-r} (1-t)(1-r-t)(1-t)^s dt + \int_{1-r}^1 (1-t)(t+r-1)(1-t)^s dt \right\} |f''(b)| \\ &= [\Pi_{13}(r, s) + \Pi_{14}(r, s)] |f''(a)| + [\Pi_{11}(r, s) + \Pi_{12}(r, s)] |f''(b)|, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Hence, if $0 \leq r \leq \frac{1}{2}$ then by (6)-(7), we get

$$\frac{2}{(b-a)^2} |N_a^b(f)(r, s)|$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq [\Pi_{11}(r, s) + \Pi_{12}(r, s) + \Pi_{13}(r, s) + \Pi_{14}(r, s)] |f''(a)| \\ &+ [\Pi_{11}(r, s) + \Pi_{12}(r, s) + \Pi_{13}(r, s) + \Pi_{14}(r, s)] |f''(b)|. \end{aligned}$$

(b) If $\frac{1}{2} \leq r \leq 1$, and fact that $|f''|$ is s -convex function, we have

$$\begin{aligned} P_{11} &= \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} |t(1-t)| \{t^s |f''(a)| + (1-t)^s |f''(b)|\} dt \\ &= \left(\frac{2r(s+3) - (s+2)}{2^{s+3}(s+1)(s+2)(s+3)} \right) |f''(a)| + \left(\frac{s^2+7s+14-2r(s+2)^2-2^{s+4}}{2^{s+3}(s+1)(s+2)(s+3)} \right) |f''(b)|, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

and similarly, we have

$$\begin{aligned} P_{22} &= \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^1 |(1-t)(1-r-t)| \{t^s |f''(a)| + (1-t)^s |f''(b)|\} dt \\ &= \left(\frac{s^2+7s+14-2r(s+2)^2-2^{s+4}}{2^{s+3}(s+1)(s+2)(s+3)} \right) |f''(a)| + \left(\frac{2r(s+3) - (s+2)}{2^{s+3}(s+1)(s+2)(s+3)} \right) |f''(b)|. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, if $\frac{1}{2} \leq r \leq 1$ then by (8),(9) and(5), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{2}{(b-a)^2} |N_a^b(f)(r, s)| \\ &\leq \left(\frac{2(s+3) - r - 2^{s+3}}{2^{s+3}(s+1)(s+2)(s+3)} \right) [|f''(a)| + |f''(b)|] \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

This completes the proof.

Corollary 1 (a) In Theorem 11 (a),

(1) If we put $r = 0$ and $s = 1$, we have

$$|N_a^b(f)(0, 1)| \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{48} [|f''(a)| + |f''(b)|]$$

(2) If we put $r = \frac{1}{3}$ and $s = 1$, we have

$$\left| N_a^b(f) \left(\frac{1}{3}, 1 \right) \right| \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{162} [|f''(a)| + |f''(b)|]$$

Corollary 2 (a) In Theorem 11 (b),

(1) If we put $r = 1$ and $s = 1$, we have

$$|N_a^b(f)(1,1)| \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{48} [|f''(a)| + |f''(b)|]$$

(2) If we put $r = \frac{2}{3}$ and $s = 1$, we have

$$|N_a^b(f)\left(\frac{2}{3}, 1\right)| \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{48} [|f''(a)| + |f''(b)|]$$

Theorem 12 Under the assumptions of Lemma 1 holds. If

$|f''|^q$ is s -convex function on $[a, b]$ and $q \geq 1$, then following inequality holds:

(a) for $0 \leq r \leq \frac{1}{2}$:

$$|N_a^b(f)(r, s)| \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{2} \left(\frac{8r^3 - 3r + 1}{24}\right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \times \left[\left\{ (\Pi_{11}(r, s) + \Pi_{12}(r, s)) |f''(a)|^q + (\Pi_{13}(r, s) + \Pi_{14}(r, s)) |f''(b)|^q \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left\{ (\Pi_{13}(r, s) + \Pi_{14}(r, s)) |f''(b)|^q + (\Pi_{11}(r, s) + \Pi_{12}(r, s)) |f''(a)|^q \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}} \right]$$

for $\frac{1}{2} \leq r \leq 1$:

$$|N_a^b(f)(r, s)| \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{2} \left(\frac{8r^3 - 3r + 1}{24}\right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left[\left\{ (\Pi_{21}(r, s) |f''(a)|^q + \Pi_{31}(r, s) |f''(b)|^q) + \left\{ (\Pi_{31}(r, s) |f''(a)|^q + \Pi_{21}(r, s) |f''(b)|^q) \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}} \right]$$

Proof. Using the lemma 1, Hölder's inequality and fact that

$|f''|^q$ is s -convex function, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{2}{(b-a)^2} |N_a^b(f)(r, s)| \\ & \leq \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} |t(t-r)| |f''(ta + (1-t)b)| dt + \\ & \leq \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^1 |(1-t)(1-r-t)| |f''(ta + (1-t)b)| dt \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \leq \left(\frac{8r^3 - 3r + 1}{24}\right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left[\left(\int_0^r |t(t-r)| |f''(ta + (1-t)b)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ & \left. + \left(\int_r^1 |(1-t)(1-r-t)| |f''(ta + (1-t)b)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ & = \left(\frac{8r^3 - 3r + 1}{24}\right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left[D_{21}^q + D_{22}^q \right]. \end{aligned}$$

(a) for $0 \leq r \leq \frac{1}{2}$ and fact that $|f''|$ is s -convex function, we have

$$\begin{aligned} D_{21} & = \left\{ \int_0^r t^{s+1}(r-t) dt + \int_r^{\frac{1}{2}} t^{s+1}(t-r) dt \right\} |f''(a)|^q \\ & + \left\{ \int_0^r t(1-t)^s(r-t) dt + \int_r^{\frac{1}{2}} t(1-t)^s(t-r) dt \right\} |f''(b)|^q \\ & = \left\{ (\Pi_{11}(r, s) + \Pi_{12}(r, s)) |f''(a)|^q + (\Pi_{13}(r, s) + \Pi_{14}(r, s)) |f''(b)|^q \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}}, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$D_{22} = \left\{ (\Pi_{13}(r, s) + \Pi_{14}(r, s)) |f''(b)|^q + (\Pi_{11}(r, s) + \Pi_{12}(r, s)) |f''(a)|^q \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}},$$

we use the equality (9)-(10), then the part (a) is proved.

(b) For $\frac{1}{2} \leq r \leq 1$, and fact that $|f''|$ is s -convex function, we have

$$\begin{aligned} D_{21} & \leq \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} |t(t-r)| \{ t^s |f''(a)| + (1-t)^s |f''(b)| \} dt \\ & = \Pi_{21}(r, s) |f''(a)|^q + \Pi_{31}(r, s) |f''(b)|^q, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$D_{22} = \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^1 |(1-t)(1-r-t)| \{ t^s |f''(a)| + (1-t)^s |f''(b)| \} dt$$

$$= \left(\Pi_{31}(r, s) |f''(a)|^q + \Pi_{21}(r, s) |f''(b)|^q \right).$$

Hence, if $\frac{1}{2} \leq r \leq 1$, then (11), (12) and (5), we have

$$\frac{2}{(b-a)^2} |N_a^b(f)(r, s)| \leq \left(\frac{8r^3 - 3r + 1}{24} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \left[\left(\Pi_{21}(r, s) |f''(a)|^q + \Pi_{31}(r, s) |f''(b)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\Pi_{31}(r, s) |f''(a)|^q + \Pi_{21}(r, s) |f''(b)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right].$$

This completes the proof.

Corollary 3 In Theorem 12 (a) if we put $r = 0$ and $s = 1$, then we have

$$|N_a^b(f)(0, 1)| \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{48} \left[\left(\frac{3|f''(a)|^q + 5|f''(b)|^q}{8} \right) + \left(\frac{5|f''(a)|^q + 3|f''(b)|^q}{8} \right) \right],$$

where we using the $\Pi_{11}(0, 1) = 0$, $\Pi_{12}(0, 1) = \frac{1}{64}$ and

$$\Pi_{21}(0, 1) = \frac{5}{192}.$$

(b) In Theorem 12 (b)

(a) If we put $r = \frac{1}{3}$, then we have

$$|N_a^b(f)\left(\frac{1}{3}, s\right)| \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{162} \left[\frac{\left(\Pi_{41}\left(\frac{1}{3}, s\right) |f''(a)|^q + \Pi_{51}\left(\frac{1}{3}, s\right) |f''(b)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}}}{3^4} + \frac{\left(\Pi_{51}\left(\frac{1}{3}, s\right) |f''(a)|^q + \Pi_{41}\left(\frac{1}{3}, s\right) |f''(b)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}}}{3^4} \right],$$

where

$$\Pi_{41}\left(\frac{1}{3}, s\right) = \frac{2^{s+4} + 3^{s+2} s}{6^{s+3} (s+2)(s+3)}.$$

$$\Pi_{51}\left(\frac{1}{3}, s\right) = \frac{7(4^{s+3}) - 3^{s+3}(8 + 2^{s+3}) + (4^{s+3} + 2 \cdot 6^{s+2} - 3^{s+4})s - 3^{s+2} s^2}{6^{s+3} (s+1)(s+2)(s+3)}.$$

(b) If we put $r = \frac{1}{3}$ and $s = 1$, then we have (14)

$$|N_a^b(f)\left(\frac{1}{3}, 1\right)| \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{162} \left[\left(\frac{59|f''(a)|^q + 133|f''(b)|^q}{192} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{133|f''(a)|^q + 59|f''(b)|^q}{192} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right].$$

(c) If we put $r = 1$ and $s = 1$, then we have

$$|N_a^b(f)(1, 1)| \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{162} \left(\frac{27}{4} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \left[\left(\frac{11|f''(a)|^q + 5|f''(b)|^q}{16} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{5|f''(a)|^q + 11|f''(b)|^q}{16} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right].$$

3 Conclusion

This study highlights the importance of fractional integral inequalities as a crucial tool in the development of various fields within pure and applied mathematics. In recent years, several researchers have introduced generalized inequalities involving fractional integral operators. My primary goal is to investigate a unified method focusing on the midpoint and trapezoid rules and explore how these fractional inequalities can be derived by incorporating the concept of s-convex functions through the Caputo-Fabrizio integral operator. Additionally, new identity for twice differentiable functions in the framework of the Caputo-Fabrizio fractional operator have been examined. Based on the new established identity as supporting results, the research proposed new error bounds for fractional versions of the midpoint and trapezoid rules, utilizing classical inequalities like Hölder's and power-mean inequalities. Furthermore, by substituting specific values obtained from previous results, the precision and applicability of the existing findings were significantly enhanced.

Declaration of Ethical Standards: Not applicable.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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